

PREPAREDNESS LEVEL OF FLOOD-PRONE RESIDENTS IN A SELECTED LOCAL COMMUNITY

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ABSTRACT

Natural disasters often occur unexpectedly, with floods identified as the most common type. Being prepared is essential in mitigating possible hazards. This study determined the preparedness level of flood-prone residents in a selected local community. Specifically, it sought to describe the respondents' demographic profile by age and sex, and to assess their preparedness in terms of awareness and knowledge of flood hazards, availability of emergency supplies and resources, and community participation and disaster response training. A descriptive research design was used to administer a researchers-made survey instrument to 267 flood-prone residents. Statistical techniques such as mean and standard deviation were used in the study. The findings revealed a very high level of preparedness when participants were grouped according to sex and age. Among the dimensions, awareness and knowledge about flood hazards obtained with the highest mean score, followed by availability of emergency supplies and resources, and community participation and disaster response training. Overall, the findings indicated that the flood-prone residents exhibited strong preparedness levels. The study recommends an enhanced Barangay plan to strengthen community participation and disaster response initiatives.

Keywords: *Preparedness Level, Awareness and Knowledge about Flood Hazards, Availability of Emergency Supplies and Resources, Community Participation and Disaster Response Training, Descriptive Quantitative Research Design*

INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters come quickly and sometimes without warning. They can be a series of catastrophic events stemming from various natural phenomena on planet Earth, including earthquakes, hurricanes, tsunamis, and typhoon-related floods (Gupta, 2024). Floods are the most frequent disaster type, accounting for about 44% of all disaster events registered in the first two decades of this century, and affect the most significant number of people worldwide (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, 2025). A flood occurs when water overflows and submerges land that is usually dry. It is mainly caused by heavy rainfall, storm surges from tropical cyclones, or tsunamis in coastal regions (World Health Organization, 2021). Good preparation and knowing what to do in a flood will increase personal safety and chances of survival if it happens in the area. It can also help minimize potential flood damage and accelerate recovery efforts.

Researchers from China developed a hypothesis about preparedness measures for rural residents during flooding. According to Ao et. al. (2020), discussed that 46.5% of the respondents adopted poor level of disaster preparedness behavior ranging from 0 to 2, whereas very few respondents were well prepared, specifically 2.42% had 12–14 disaster preparedness level, and that flood experience and disposition towards disaster also impacts preparedness behavior. Another study assessed flood preparedness and literacy among elders through a SWOT analysis in Bangkok, Thailand, revealing that 50.32% of Bangkok's total area was highly flood-prone and that 86% of respondents had never participated in community training on flood preparedness and management. In comparison, the remaining 22% were defined as prepared for disasters (Sawangnate et al., 2022). In Bangladesh, Islam et al. (2020) revealed the dominant factors that regulate community participation in sustainable disaster recovery programming and factors that control decision making participation such as disaster management system, leadership decentralization, community capacity building, community resources, and disaster experiences and vulnerability. In addition, the factors associated with the type of community participation fall variably along structural, operational, community, and participant domains.

In the Philippines, a study found that residents in riverine flood-affected areas in Davao City must be well-informed and prepared during floods, focusing solely on levels of disaster preparedness and residents' locations (Avelino, 2024). According to the Republic of the Philippines: Survey on Disaster Preparedness and Climate Change Perceptions (2024), 70% of Filipino citizens monitored typhoon and other disaster warnings, 60% familiarized the rainfall warnings, 58% of those citizens discussed emergency plans as a family, 20% have prepared disaster management plan, and 33% for preparing first aid kits, implying that the Filipinos routinely experience water-related hazards, such as floods.

Several studies have been conducted relative to the disaster preparedness. For instance, in the study of Caoleng and Fermin (2024), mentioned that households in Pura, Tarlac exhibited varying levels of preparedness, depending on the availability and completeness of their emergency supplies. The results showed that families who maintain

essential resources such as stocked food, first aid kits, flashlights, whistles, and radios report feeling very prepared to face disasters or emergencies. These supplies not only support immediate survival needs but also enhance the respondents' ability to respond effectively during power outages, injuries, or evacuation scenarios. In contrast, a substantial portion of the respondents identified themselves as only somewhat prepared due to incomplete emergency kits, particularly the lack of flashlights and first-aid supplies. Moreover, a smaller group reported not being prepared, often linked to financial limitations that hinder their ability to maintain adequate food supplies or acquire essential equipment. Likewise, in the study's findings of Lopez et al. (2022) revealed a great extent of disaster preparedness practices with significant differences when respondents were grouped according to household income and educational attainment of the household members. However, there were no significant differences when grouped according to household size, type of housing unit, and type of housing structure. Household income is very minimal in purchasing food/kit supplies were identified as the most significant challenge experienced by the households.

Moreover, Ben-Enukora et al. (2025), mentioned that households living in flood-prone communities exhibited varying levels of awareness and knowledge, depending on their access to reliable information. Their findings revealed that early warning often delivered via radio, Facebook, and especially through community leaders play a vital role in shaping residents' understanding of flood risks and encouraging precautionary actions. Similarly, Arana-Ruedas et al. (2023) emphasized that public knowledge and perception are essential for effective risk-management strategies, noting that well-informed communities are more proactive and more likely to support adaptation measures. Their respondents valued natural systems for hazard management and preferred participatory approaches over top-down approaches, highlighting how trust, information access, and community engagement influence people's readiness for disasters. Together, these studies show that awareness and access to credible information strongly contribute to improving communities' preparedness for flood events. In addition, according to Kurata et al. (2023), flooding remains one of the most common and damaging natural hazards, threatening people's safety, property, and livelihoods. In the Philippines, frequent typhoons, monsoon rains, and heavy rainfall make floods a recurring national concern, highlighting the importance of public awareness and knowledge about these hazards.

Numerous studies have explored various dimensions of natural disasters, particularly community resilience and preparedness. This study is particularly significant as it seeks to fill the gap in the current literature by examining the preparedness level of flood-prone areas in one of the selected local communities. This study aims to provide concrete data and information to support an analysis that better measures residents' preparedness levels during floods.

Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the preparedness level of flood-prone residents in a selected local community for 2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the residents when grouped according to:
 - a. age; and
 - b. sex?
2. What is the preparedness level of the flood-prone residents in terms of awareness and knowledge about flood hazards, availability of emergency supplies and resources, and community participation and disaster response training when taken as a whole and when grouped according to the mentioned variables?

Scope of the Study

This study identified the preparedness level of flood-prone residents of a selected local community in terms of awareness and knowledge about flood hazards; availability of emergency supplies and resources; and community participation and disaster response training. The researchers used survey questionnaires to gather the data needed for the study.

METHODOLOGY

This section outlined the method and procedures used to conduct the study. It includes the research design, respondents, locale, research instruments, and statistical treatment of the data. This study aimed to determine the preparedness level of flood-prone residents in a selected local community for 2025, using concrete data gathered through a structured questionnaire.

Research design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design. Descriptive research is a research method used to determine the characteristics of a population or a particular phenomenon (Shinija, 2024). The descriptive approach accurately captured respondents' profiles and described their level of flood preparedness without manipulating any variables. This research study used a structured survey questionnaire to identify the preparedness levels of residents regarding awareness and knowledge of flood hazards, availability of emergency supplies and resources, community participation, and disaster response training.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were flood-prone residents of a selected local community in Negros Occidental. Before selecting participants, the researchers identified flood-prone areas within the local community. After determining these areas, each was assigned a number, and researchers used a random number generator to select the study participants. In which each individual in the area was identified according to the respondents' demographic profiles, such as age and sex. The respondents were selected for this study primarily to identify residents' preparedness levels regarding awareness and knowledge of flood hazards, availability of emergency supplies and resources, community

participation, and disaster response training. Cluster sampling was used to select the participants in this study. Cluster sampling is a method in which the population is divided into naturally occurring groups, or clusters, and a random sample of these clusters is selected for study (Alex, 2024).

Research Locale

The research study was conducted in a selected local community in one of the municipalities in Negros Occidental, a coastal community that often faced flooding. This area is highly susceptible to flooding, with water levels rising to neck-deep during heavy rainfall, typhoons, or rising sea levels. Such conditions often disrupt residents' daily lives and pose serious risks to safety, property, and the residents involved.

Research Instrument

The researchers used the structured survey questionnaire to determine the preparedness level of flood-prone residents in a selected local community. The researchers employed a 5-point Likert-scale questionnaire with the following descriptive categories: 1- Unprepared, 2- Slightly Prepared, 3- Somewhat Prepared, 4- Always Prepared, and 5- Highly Prepared.

The researchers' survey questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part I pertained to the Demographic Profile of the participants, including sex and age, and Part II comprised statements designed to assess residents' preparedness levels regarding awareness and knowledge of flood hazards, availability of emergency supplies and resources, community participation, and disaster response training. There were 10 statements for each category.

The researchers validated the instrument by consulting three experts to ensure it measures what it intends to measure. The research instrument had a validity index of 3.4, indicating a good instrument.

After validation, the research instrument underwent reliability testing. The researchers conducted the reliability testing in another barangay with 30 flood-prone residents. The reliability index, as measured by Cronbach's Alpha, was 0.900, indicating strong reliability. This suggested that the items in the measure consistently measure the same underlying construct, making it a strong and dependable tool for the research.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To provide accurate answers to the specific problems raised in this study, the researchers utilized the following statistical tools for the processing and analysis of data:

Frequency and Percentage: These were used to describe the demographic profile of the 267 respondents in terms of sex and age brackets

Mean: This was employed to determine the level of preparedness of the residents across three key areas: awareness and knowledge, availability of resources, and community participation.

Standard Deviation: This was used to measure the dispersion, or variability, of residents' scores around the mean, providing insight into the consistency of their preparedness across categories.

Interpretation of Data: Preparedness levels were evaluated using a mean range scale with the following verbal interpretations: 4.21–5.00 Very High, 3.41–4.20 High, 2.61–3.40 Average, 1.81–2.60 Low, and 1.00–1.80 Very Low.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers requested the necessary data from the selected local community: a list of residents to determine the population size. Then, the researchers developed a validated survey questionnaire. After validation, the researchers conducted reliability testing with 30 flood-prone residents from another local community to assess the instrument's consistency. Once reliable, the researchers administered the research instrument to the actual respondents of the study. Moreover, the collected data were then tabulated and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings on the preparedness level of flood-prone residents of a selected local community. The analysis focused on respondents' demographic profiles and their preparedness for flood hazards. Specifically, the study examines residents' age and sex to understand better the characteristics of the community being assessed.

The implications of these findings are analyzed to identify existing gaps in preparedness and assess how they may affect the safety, resilience, and overall disaster readiness of the local community.

Demographic Profile Assessment

Table 1 shows that the study involved 267 respondents (100%). When grouped by sex, the majority of respondents were female 152 (56.9%), while 115 (43.1%) were male, indicating a higher participation of female respondents in the study.

Table 1.
Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variables	f	%
A. As a whole	267	100
B. Sex		

Male	115	43.1
Female	152	56.9
C. Age		
20- 30 years old	54	20.2
31- 40 years old	43	16.1
41- 50 years old	51	19.1
51- 60 years old	62	23.2
61- 70 years old	57	21.3

In terms of age, the largest proportion of respondents came from the 51–60 years old bracket, with 62 individuals (23.2%), followed by the 61–70 years old group with 57 individuals (21.3%), and the 20–30 years old group with 54 individuals (20.2%). On the other hand, a smaller number of respondents belonged to the 41–50 years old group (51 individuals, 19.1%) and the 31–40 years old group (43 individuals, 16.1%). This distribution suggests that the respondents were predominantly from the older age brackets, though all age groups were represented in the study.

Preparedness Level of Flood-Prone Residents

This section examined the preparedness level of flood-prone residents of a selected community across three key areas: Awareness and Knowledge about Flood Hazards, focusing on residents’ understanding of flood risks, warning systems, and safety measures; Availability of Emergency Supplies and Resources, assessing the presence of essential items such as first aid kits, food, water, evacuation plans, and communication tools; and Community Participation and Disaster Response Training, evaluating residents’ involvement in disaster preparedness programs, drills, and community-based initiatives.

These areas are analyzed based on survey responses to determine the overall level of preparedness and variations across age and sex groups. The findings aimed to identify strengths and areas for improvement in enhancing disaster readiness and community resilience.

Awareness and Knowledge about Flood Hazards

As shown in Table 2.1, the level of preparedness of flood-prone residents in terms of awareness and knowledge about flood hazards, when taken as a whole, is Very High ($M= 4.58$, $SD= 0.48$), indicating that the residents generally possess an excellent understanding and comprehensive knowledge regarding the risks and nature of flood hazards in their area.

Table 2.1
Awareness and Knowledge about Flood Hazards

Variables	Mean	Interpretation	SD
A. As a whole	4.58	Very High	0.48
B. Sex			
Male	4.65	Very High	0.40
Female	4.52	Very High	0.52
C. Age			
20- 30 years old	4.52	Very High	0.53
31- 40 years old	4.55	Very High	0.41
41- 50 years old	4.61	Very High	0.47
51- 60 years old	4.63	Very High	0.45
61- 70 years old	4.55	Very High	0.52

Regarding sex, both male (M = 4.65, SD = 0.40) and female (M = 4.52, SD = 0.52) residents exhibit Very High levels of awareness. By age, all groups achieved a Very High level, with the 51–60 years old bracket obtaining the highest mean (M= 4.63, SD= 0.45), while the 41–50 years old (M= 4.61, SD= 0.47), 31–40 years old (M= 4.55, SD= 0.41), 61–70 years old (M= 4.55, SD= 0.52), and 20–30 years old (M= 4.52, SD= 0.53) groups also demonstrate exceptional preparedness.

This indicated that most residents, regardless of demographic profile, have a strong foundation in flood hazard awareness. The high mean scores across all age groups suggest that knowledge is well distributed throughout the community, likely due to lived experience or effective local information campaigns.

Based on studies regarding disaster management and risk perception, individuals in the 51 to 60 age group frequently possess more knowledge about flood hazards due to a combination of cumulative lived experience, higher engagement in community roles, and, in some cases, greater access to traditional warning systems (Li & Wang, 2025). This knowledge of pre-elderly adults could be used as leverage to mentor younger residents or people who are slightly lower-scoring brackets to maintain this robust level of community resilience.

According to Zabini et al. (2021), people's perception of flood risk is shaped by demographics, past flood experiences, and proximity to areas at risk. The study found that individuals living near rivers who had previously experienced flood damage had a higher perception of risk. Emotional reactions, like worrying about family and property, also heightened awareness and concern about flood risks.

Availability of Emergency Supplies and Resources

As presented in Table 2.2, the level of preparedness of flood-prone residents in terms of availability of emergency supplies and resources, when taken as a whole, is Very High ($M= 4.34$, $SD= 0.63$), indicating that the residents generally maintain an excellent stock of essential materials and resources needed for flood emergencies.

Table 2.2
Availability of Emergency Supplies and Resources

Variables	Mean	Interpretation	SD
A. As a whole	4.34	Very High	0.63
B. Sex			
Male	4.42	Very High	0.58
Female	4.28	Very High	0.66
C. Age			
20- 30 years old	4.39	Very High	0.56
31- 40 years old	4.35	Very High	0.65
41- 50 years old	4.38	Very High	0.65
51- 60 years old	4.35	Very High	0.67
61- 70 years old	4.25	Very High	0.65

In terms sex, both male ($M = 4.42$, $SD = 0.58$) and female ($M = 4.28$, $SD = 0.66$) residents exhibit Very High levels of resource preparedness. By age, all groups achieved a Very High level, with the 20–30 years old bracket obtaining the highest mean ($M= 4.39$, $SD= 0.56$), while the 41–50 years old ($M= 4.38$, $SD= 0.65$), 31–40 years old ($M= 4.35$, $SD= 0.65$), 51–60 years old ($M= 4.35$, $SD= 0.67$), and 61–70 years old ($M= 4.25$, $SD= 0.65$) groups also demonstrate exceptional preparedness in terms of supplies.

This indicates that most residents, regardless of demographic profile, have a solid, consistent foundation for securing physical emergency resources. The high mean scores across all age groups suggested that the community recognized the practical importance of being equipped for a disaster, with younger adults (20–30 years old) showing a slightly higher proactive lead in resource gathering.

Chen et al. (2022) noted that the frequent occurrence of various sudden natural disasters worldwide has caused significant losses to human life. It is vital to forecast demand for emergency materials to protect people's safety and well-being. Similar to our study, the researchers found that emergency supplies are important for residents affected by natural disasters, such as flooding.

Community Participation and Disaster Response Training

As indicated in Table 2.3, the level of preparedness of flood-prone residents in terms of community participation and disaster response training, when taken as a whole, is Very High (M= 4.25, SD= 0.75). This indicates that the residents generally actively engage in local safety initiatives and have a strong commitment to formal training for disaster scenarios.

Table 2.3
Community Participation and Disaster Response Training

Variables	Mean	Interpretation	SD
A. As a whole	4.25	Very High	0.75
B. Sex			
Male	4.42	Very High	0.64
Female	4.13	High	0.80
C. Age			
20- 30 years old	4.27	Very High	0.60
31- 40 years old	4.27	Very High	0.74
41- 50 years old	4.05	High	0.82
51-60 years old	4.34	Very High	0.78
61 70 years old	4.31	Very High	0.76

By sex, males exhibit a Very High level (M= 4.42, SD= 0.64), while females are rated as High (M= 4.13, SD= 0.80). By age, most groups achieved a Very High level, with the 51–60 years old bracket obtaining the highest mean (M= 4.34, SD= 0.78), while the 61–70 years old (M= 4.31, SD= 0.76), 20–30 years old (M= 4.27, SD= 0.60), and 31–40 years old (M= 4.27, SD= 0.74) groups also demonstrate exceptional participation. The 41–50-year-old group exhibited a High level of preparedness (M = 4.05, SD = 0.82).

This implied that most residents, regardless of their demographic profile, have a solid, consistent foundation in community-based disaster response. The high mean scores across most age groups suggested a culture of collective responsibility. However, the "High" rather than "Very High" rating among females and in the 41–50 age bracket suggested that these groups may face time constraints or accessibility issues that slightly limit their participation compared to peers. Overall, the community demonstrates strong readiness to act together, which is vital for effective local disaster management.

The results of this study are similar to those of the case study in Songkar Village by Hendra & Kismartini (2018) it was revealed that community involvement plays a crucial role in effective flood disaster management. The findings showed that residents actively participated in planning, implementation, and maintenance activities related to disaster risk reduction. The study emphasized that cooperation between community members, local organizations, and government agencies strengthens disaster preparedness and

promotes a culture of safety within flood-prone areas. It concluded that sustainable disaster management depends on consistent and organized community participation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers made the following conclusions:

The demographic profiles showed that the majority of respondents were female, with the largest proportion from the 51–60 years old bracket.

When taken as a whole, the respondents demonstrated a very high level of awareness and knowledge of flood hazards and the availability of emergency supplies and resources, regardless of age or sex. Meanwhile, regarding sex, statistics showed that male respondents had a very high level of community participation and disaster response training, and participants aged 51-60 had a very high level of preparedness, compared with those aged 41-50.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

For Flood-prone residents: Residents are encouraged to not only maintain their personal emergency supplies but also to take an active role in community-led disaster planning to foster collective resilience.

For Community leaders: Leaders may establish a localized communication system or "buddy system" that leverages the high level of individual awareness.

For the Local Government Unit Officials (LGUs): To perform immediate action and programs that would help gain awareness and readiness among younger residents regarding flood occurrences.

Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Officers: DRRM Officers may design more interactive, frequent community-based drills and disaster response training sessions to increase participation rates and residents' practical skills.

For Future researchers: Future Researchers may conduct similar studies using inferential statistics to determine if a significant relationship exists between age or sex and the overall level of disaster preparedness, or to explore the specific barriers to community training participation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured that this study on the preparedness levels of flood-prone residents strictly followed ethical guidelines in conducting the research, protecting

respondents' rights and the integrity of the research process. Before data collection, participants were informed of the study's purpose. Participants were also informed that their participation is voluntary and that they can withdraw from the study at any time if they refuse to cooperate. All personal information about the participants, such as names, was optional, treated confidentially, and used solely for academic and research purposes. All data gathered were interpreted honestly and objectively in accordance with the research objectives, without bias or manipulation. The researchers properly cited all sources to avoid plagiarism. Additionally, the study was conducted with the knowledge and approval of local authorities and complied with institutional ethical guidelines for research involving human participants.

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